

WAYS OF VIRTUAL INTERNATIONALIZATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION: INCREASING THE LEVEL OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE PROFICIENCY

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses one aspect of internationalization in higher education, namely, the improvement of proficiency in foreign languages. It outlines the activities that form the basis for the process of teaching foreign languages at the Department of Foreign Languages and Translation of the National Aviation University, both in classroom and extracurricular settings.

Keywords: foreign language, higher education, internationalization, online education, student scientific club.

FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM

Virtual internationalization of higher education is an integrative process utilizing information and communication technologies, involving the coordinated integration of international, intercultural, or global dimensions into the goals, functions, and providing processes of higher education. The purpose of virtual internationalization of higher education is to improve the quality of education and research, which will contribute to the development of society and solve global problems" [3].

The challenge for Ukrainian education is ensuring the quality of the learning process in a classroom setting during a state of war, characterized by a negative impact on the psychophysiological health of students and educators, constant excessive tension, threats, and instability. Educators are under stress and anxiety due to the responsibility not only for their own lives, and those of their loved ones but also for organizing the timely evacuation of students to shelters. Despite these challenges, teachers conduct classes offline and keep virtual classes to ensure equal opportunities and access to educational services for all students.

ANALYSIS OF RECENT RESEARCH AND PUBLICATIONS

Prokofieva M. and Sabitova A. [8] reported the results of practical activities contributing to the improvement of students' foreign language proficiency in online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic, which remains relevant for virtual classrooms. The potential of podcasting technology in developing the foreign language competence of future translators was studied by O. Kovtun, T. Harmash, and N. Khaidari [6]. N.

Glushanytsya and T. Tarnavska T. considered the use of information technologies (web application Padlet, speech recognition technologies "Speech Recognition", web tool to record sound, online audio editor Vacaroo, and others) to form and develop the secondary linguistic identity of Bachelors and Masters [1]. L. Konoplianyk studied the benefits in teaching and learning the "Professional Foreign language" disciplines applying the virtual tools such as Quizlet, Eddpuzzle, Liveworksheets, Mentimeter, Google Forms, Flipgrid [7]. L. Konoplianyk also supports the use of digital platforms and applications to implement the important components of educational process during a semester. [7].

However, in our opinion, the issue of quality teaching of foreign languages using virtual resources requires further exploration works.

THE PURPOSE OF THE WORK

We will consider one aspect of ensuring the virtual internationalization of domestic education - the improvement of students' proficiency in foreign languages and consider the activities that contribute to it. In our opinion, proficiency in a foreign language contributes to the realization of the following opportunities: academic mobility of students; participation in international programs and projects; expanding access to new knowledge; and employment of graduates in international companies [2].

RESULTS

As we mentioned above, Prokofieva M. and Sabitova A. examined virtual resources for learning foreign languages and described their results [8]. We provide them below in the table 1.

Table 1.

Virtual resources for learning foreign languages

Resource	Learning outcomes
access to digital platforms and tools of the Google Classroom	increasing the students' interest and motivation
external platforms (Moodle, Web Course Tools) and internal platforms (Macmillan English Campus, CALL).	ensuring the educational process and the possibility of developing various skills under the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, Teaching, Assessment
access to the language club from the German language school "Start Deutsch Schule" on the platform Zoom	implementation of communicative, cultural, and informational functions based on digital platforms
use of electronic resources (electronic textbooks, electronic information reference systems: electronic dictionaries, thesauruses, glossaries, electronic encyclopedias).	simplification of search activity, acceleration of the formation of professional foreign language competence in contrast to paper printing products
virtual tour of cultural and historical places	provision of cultural information
creation of a workshop based on the texts of the social, cultural, economic, and historical direction of the "German Wave" [2].	reflection of the cross-cultural aspect, the picture of the world, and the cultural codes of the country whose language is being studied

We consider it expedient to supplement the table with activities provided by the Department of Foreign Languages and Translation of the National Aviation University, namely conducting student scientific clubs, using podcasts, resources from TED talks, and Oxford Online for teaching disciplines.

Let us consider each of these positions in more detail. The teachers of the Department of Foreign Languages and Translation of the National Aviation University provide students with 8 scientific studios: "Learning a foreign language by watching videos", "Student English-speaking discussion club", "Literary and art studies", "Legal Systems of English-speaking countries", "Professional English. Record Management", "Psychological development of personality", "Social work interaction", "Professional Communication" and the elective "Swedish language". The work of these mentioned studios is aimed at enriching the vocabulary of students in domains of professional foreign language, developing reading and writing skills, listening to a foreign language, developing the ability to justify own attitude, and gaining skills in creating presentations and presenting them publicly. In addition to the improvement of a professional foreign language, students are offered the study of topics that contribute to the widening of cultural horizons and education of tolerance, increasing interest in learning foreign languages. Taking participation in the workshops of the scientific club "Legal System of English countries", students get acquainted with traditions, history, prominent figures, the education system of foreign countries, social policy, new demands of society, and the transformation of the labor market. Also, a specific value is given to the development of "soft skills". Thus, the purpose of the scientific students' unit "English Speaking Club" for technical majors is to facilitate overcoming

the language and psychology barriers, acquiring communication skills with native speakers, developing creative thinking, gaining skills in leading a discussion in a foreign language, and enhancing career motivation and oratorical skills. The elective "Swedish language" for humanities students is aimed at the formation of plurilingual competence. Participation in the above-mentioned clubs and electives allows students to study English, German, and Swedish.

In our opinion, the key goal of the students learning a foreign language is the formation of their positive emotional attitude towards the studying language. Watching good featured films and videos in foreign languages with subsequent film discussion can help to carry out the goal. The club "Learning a foreign language by watching videos" offers students a selection of interesting, meaningful, and useful from methodological and practical points of view video materials, immerses students in the language environment, which helps to effectively replenish the vocabulary, improve pronunciation and perceive the language by ear. Authentic video material viewing allows students to learn a foreign language in its most natural cultural environment, as the film provides with the necessary context for the use of the language being studied and presents fragments of the reality of the lives of its speakers.

There is a so-called instrumental motivation, which theoretically convinces the student to study the subject, and supports and drives their actions with grades, including those on exams. This type of motivation is appropriately called external, as it involves a system of means and actions imposed by the school or university from the outside, engaging students in the most challenging activities.

Among the factors contributing to successful language acquisition, instrumental motivation holds a

prominent place, which can be significantly enhanced by well-chosen forms and methods of organizing the learning process, such as web quests. The founders of the WebQuest concept see it as an investigative activity where most or all information is sourced from the Internet. Web quests are designed to focus students on using information rather than searching for it, fostering students' thinking at the levels of analysis, synthesis, and evaluation. Applying a constructivist approach to teaching, web quests facilitate the development of imagination, problem-solving skills, creative and critical thinking, and the ability to conclude moral and ethical decisions based on facts [9]. As an example, N. Glushanitsa cites the web quest "Chasing Carmen Digital Escape Room", developed by Lauren Ruri and Felicia Brock, librarians serving adults at the Washington-Centerville Public Library in Centerville, Ohio, used in teaching the discipline "Professional Foreign Language" for the "Design" as a major [1].

The researcher L. Konoplianyk emphasizes the provision of the formative assessment of students by ensuring a special adjustment for each topic of students. L. Konoplianyk explored resourceful usage of online tools for quizzes and polls as productive instruments for formative assessment to form students' criticism in monitoring their achievements to naissance students' self-motivation in learning progress as personal development [7, pp. 102, 109].

The integrative motivation, which immigrants acquire when settling in another country or individuals marrying into a different linguistic community, significantly differs from instrumental motivation. The most success is likely achieved in mixed cases. Nevertheless, integrative motivation yields better results, especially when people tend to prioritize goals such as the speed of language acquisition and achieving a level essential for survival in the country of the studied language. This motivation requires action and problem-solving respectively. So, it becomes a motivation for communication because tasks must be completed to achieve the goal [4, p. 13].

In our study of the action-oriented approach to teaching and learning a foreign language, we found that this approach helps to create a kind of integrative motivation through professionally and practically significant situations. Students learn to use the foreign language authentically for communication in a team, find common solutions, and practice scenarios related to their future professional activities [4]. Examples of using this approach were provided in the course "Practical Course of the Second Foreign Language and Translation, German" [2, p. 14].

Practical tasks such as extracting specific information from a text, finding various ticket options for a route, planning a trip using Google Maps, shopping at a supermarket, ordering food through apps, seeking advice on online forums, and simulating real-life situations. Students encounter situations with practical significance, fostering curiosity and motivation for execution.

Additional examples of such tasks include planning a trip or vacation, researching culture and places

online, discussing and planning events, exchanging information on forums, exploring and discussing intercultural issues and solutions, messaging on WhatsApp, Viber, Telegram, sharing vacation photos on Instagram, and creating a photo album or collage [4, p. 14].

TED talks resources for teaching a professional foreign language (English) contain the potential for the formation of speech competence in sociology students, as it takes into account motivational-value, cognitive, activity, and emotional components and is equipped with technical capabilities for training listening, speaking, reading, writing skills, phonetics, vocabulary, and grammar [5].

Among the advantages of students' independent work with video interviews is that the teacher has the opportunity to control what and how students study outside the classroom, identify typical mistakes and adjust the teaching of the discipline, analyze the individual work of each student. The disadvantages include the lack of an automated system for checking the correctness of answers, counting the number of attempts to complete tasks and/or viewing interviews, reporting errors, and the pace of task execution.

Using the resources developed by the University of Oxford - Oxford Online, for teaching the discipline "Business foreign language", you can choose videos on the following topics: "How to Negotiate in English" [10]; "Write a CV for an English-Speaking Job". "Tips to Write a Great Resume" [11]; "English Job Interview Tips and Tricks"; "How to Answer Job Interview Questions in English" [12] and others.

Tests of 20 questions are offered to check understanding of the topic. Oxford Online developers provide high-quality professional content that reflects modern business communication standards; offer a variety of topics (from business vocabulary to public speaking and negotiations, covering various aspects of business language); language is produced by native speakers; developed language exercises and testing; the flexibility of the learning process (the ability to choose your own pace) and online availability are ensured.

The results of the incorporation of the listening module in the independent study schedule are:

- ✓ regular organized independent work by students;
- ✓ overcoming language barriers for students;
- ✓ development of students' self-reflection and academic autonomy.

CONCLUSIONS

Therefore, digital technologies are actively integrated into the educational environment, bringing international and intercultural influence. The formation of speech foreign language competence, socio-cultural, plurilingual competence of students is carried out by classroom and extracurricular work, which contributes to increasing the level of foreign language proficiency.

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